

Formalization of PABRE Security Templates

Supplementary material for the paper:

"Formalising Non-Functional Requirements
Templates for Verifiable System Design"

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1 Introduction

In this supplementary material, we provide the formalization of the full set of *Security* templates of the PABRE catalog, namely: Authentication, Authorization, Automatic Logoff, Data Transmission Protocol, and Stored Data Protection. For the formalization we use linear temporal logic, possibly enriched with time-related metrics.

Figure 1: Security templates of the PABRE catalog

2 Background: Linear Temporal Logic with Time Metrics

Linear Temporal Logic with Time Metrics extends Linear Temporal Logic by annotating temporal operators with *time intervals* [?, ?]. It is used to express constraints such as “within 5 seconds”, “for at least 10 ms”, and similar quantitative timing requirements. Formulas are evaluated over timed traces; the time domain can be either discrete (\mathbb{N}) or dense ($\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$).

Let AP be a finite set of atomic propositions, T a time domain, and \mathcal{I} the set of intervals $I \subseteq T$ (e.g., $[a, b]$, $(a, b]$, $[a, \infty)$). The syntax of Metric Temporal Logic (MTL) over AP is:

$$\phi ::= \top \mid p \mid \neg\phi \mid \phi \vee \phi \mid \mathbf{X}\phi \mid \mathbf{F}_I\phi \mid \mathbf{G}_I\phi \mid \phi \mathbf{U}_I\phi \quad (p \in \text{AP}, I \in \mathcal{I})$$

Main operators

The informal semantics of the main metric temporal operators is as follows:

- $\mathbf{G}_I \phi$ (globally on I): ϕ holds at *all* future instants whose distance lies within I .
- $\mathbf{F}_I \phi$ (eventually within I): there *exists* a future instant, at a distance in I , at which ϕ holds.
- $\phi \mathbf{U}_I \psi$ (until within I): ϕ holds *until* ψ holds at some instant whose distance lies within I (and ψ must occur within I).
- \mathbf{X} (next) is mainly meaningful in *discrete* time (next step).

Usage notes

- The *time domain* (discrete vs. dense) and the *interval convention* (open/closed) must always be specified.
- In dense time, *punctual* constraints (e.g., $= 5$) may lead to more delicate decidability issues.
- Useful identities: $\mathbf{F}_I \phi \equiv \top \mathbf{U}_I \phi$ and $\mathbf{G}_I \phi \equiv \neg \mathbf{F}_I \neg \phi$.

3 Authentication

Requirement Pattern <i>Authentication</i>	Description	This pattern expresses the need of having the system functionality to identify users	
	Comments	—	
	Pattern goal	Ensure the identity of the users that access to the system.	
	Author	GESSI-SSI	
	Sources (0..*)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement books from SSI • Specialized literature 	
	Keywords (0..*)	Access Control, Security, Users	
	Dependencies (0..*)	IMPLIES Authorization IMPLIES Stored Data Protection	
Requirement Form <i>Authentication</i>	Description	This form states the general need of having the system functionality of identifying users, and has extensions for detailing the type or technology to be used. An extension for requiring to not be necessary to create an specific account for the system is present.	
	Comments	Application of extensions: Authentication Technology, Single Sign-on: may be applied at most once each.	
	Version date	2009-03-20 00:00:00.0	
	Author	GESSI-SSI	
	Sources (0..*)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement books from SSI • Specialized literature 	
	Fixed Part	Form text	The system shall authenticate users
	Extended Part <i>Authentication Technology</i>	Form text	The authentication process shall be based on the %auth-Mechanism% authentication technology
		Parameter	Metric
		authMechanism: is an authentication software technology	AuthenticationTechnology: AuthenticationTechnology = Domain(Windows login, ...)
	Extended Part <i>Authentication Types</i>	Form text	The authentication type shall be: %authTypes%
		Parameter	Metric
authTypes: is a non-empty set of authentication types		AuthenticationTypes: AuthenticationTypes = Set(AuthenticationType) AuthenticationType = Domain(Open, Encrypted)	
Extended Part <i>Single Sign-on</i>	Form text	The system shall not oblige users to create and manage a specific account for this system	

3.1 Sets

- *Users*: Set of all users.
- *AuthTypes*: Global set of authentication types (Open, Encrypted).
- *AuthMechanism*: Set of authentication technologies.
- *SSOProviders*: Set of *SSO providers*.
- *FA*: Set of authentication factors.
- *Strings*: Set of strings.
- *RequiredCharset*: Set of character classes required for passwords.
- *RotationDays*: Set of integer values representing the number of days within which password rotation must be performed.

3.2 Predicates

- *auth(u)*: Predicate indicating that the authentication process has been initiated for user *u*.
- *authenticationCheck(u)*: Predicate indicating that user *u* has been authenticated.
- *authenticationWith(u, a)*: Predicate indicating that user *u* has been authenticated using authentication mechanism *a*.
- *typeApplied(u, t)*: Predicate indicating that authentication type *t* has been applied to user *u*.
- *authenticateVia(u, p)*: User *u* has authenticated through the *SSO provider p*.
- *createLocalAccountRequired(u)*: Predicate indicating that user *u* has been required to create a local account in order to proceed.
- *MFA(u, fa)*: Predicate indicating that user *u* has provided authentication factor *fa*.
- *LengthOK(p)*: Predicate indicating that password *p* satisfies the length constraint.

- *Contains*(p, s): Predicate indicating that password p contains character s .
- *SetPwd*(p): Predicate indicating that password p has been set.
- *PwdExpired*(p): Predicate indicating that password p has expired.
- *CountFail*(u): Predicate indicating that user u has reached *maxFailed* consecutive failed attempts.
- *Blocked*(u): Predicate indicating that user u 's account has been blocked.
- *Access*(u): Predicate indicating that user u has accessed.

3.3 Variables

- *lockoutDuration* $\in \mathbb{N}$ (unit of measure: minutes)

3.4 Formalization of the Fixed Part

$$\forall u \in Users. \mathbf{G} \left(auth(u) \rightarrow \mathbf{F} authenticationCheck(u) \right)$$

3.5 Formalization of the Extended Parts

3.5.1 Authentication Technology

$$\begin{aligned} & \exists a \in AuthMechanism. \quad \forall u \in Users. \\ & \mathbf{G} \left(auth(u) \rightarrow \mathbf{F} (authenticateWith(u, a)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

3.5.2 Authentication Type

$$\begin{aligned} & \exists t \in authTypes. \quad \forall u \in Users. \\ & \mathbf{G} \left(auth(u) \rightarrow \mathbf{F} (authenticationCheck(u) \wedge typeApplied(u, t)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

3.5.3 Single Sign-On

$$\begin{aligned} & \exists p \in SSOProviders. \quad \forall u \in Users. \\ & \mathbf{G} \left(auth(u) \rightarrow \mathbf{X} (authenticateVia(u, p)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Constraint that does not require the creation of a local account.

$$\forall u \in Users. \quad \mathbf{G} (\neg createLocalAccountRequired(u))$$

4 Authorization

Requirement Pattern <i>Authorization</i>	Description	This pattern expresses the need of having the system functionality (possibly configurable) to protect system resources from unauthorized accesses
	Comments	Is required to take into account the customers needs about user hierarchies and access rights, also is important to review the current technology about authorization mechanisms
	Pattern goal	Ensure that users access system resources according their access rights.
	Author	GESSI-SSI
	Sources (0..*)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement books from SSI • Specialized literature
	Keywords (0..*)	Security
	Dependencies (0..*)	IMPLIES Authentication IMPLIES Stored Data Protection

Requirement Form <i>Authorization</i>	Description	This form is applicable when the customer need to protect system resources from unauthorized accesses. The requirement book declares user profiles, resources, control access types and technology used, and maybe some particular authorization rules, as well as the possibility for an administrator to customize these issues.		
	Comments	Application of extensions: Authorization Profiles, Authorization Profiles Customization, Authorization Resources, Authorization Resources Customization, Authorization Control Access, Authorization Control Access Customization, Authorization Technology: may be applied at most once each.		
	Version date	2009-03-20 00:00:00.0		
	Author	GESSE-SSI		
	Sources (0..*)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement books from SSI • Specialized literature 		
	Fixed Part	Form text	The system shall control user access rights to all kind of resources.	
	Extended Part <i>Authorization Control Access</i>	Form text	The system shall control %authContAccess% access types to the resources.	
		Parameter	Metric	
		authContAccess: is a non-empty set of system control access types	ControlAccessTypes: ControlAccessTypes = Set(ControlAccessType) ControlAccessType = Domain(Read, Write, Execute, ...)	
	Extended Part <i>Authorization Control Access Customization</i>	Form text	The system shall allow an administrator to define control access to system resources.	
	Extended Part <i>Authorization Profiles</i>	Form text	The system shall recognize %userProfiles% users profiles.	
		Parameter	Metric	
userProfiles: is a non-empty set of user profiles		UserInterfaceActions: UserInterfaceActions = Set(UserInterfaceAction) UserInterfaceAction = Domain(Initial Screen Load, Transition between Screens, Complex Searches, ...)		
Extended Part <i>Authorization Profiles Customization</i>	Form text	The system shall allow an administrator to define user profiles.		
Extended Part <i>Authorization Resources</i>	Form text	The system shall manage user access rights to %resNames% resources.		
	Parameter	Metric		
	resNames: is a non-empty set of system resource	SystemResources: SystemResources = Set(SystemResource) SystemResource = Domain(Document, Section, Database,...)		
Extended Part <i>Authorization Resources Customization</i>	Form text	The system shall allow an administrator to define user access rights to system resources.		

	Extended Part <i>Authorization Rule</i>	Form text	Users with profile %userProfiles% shall have %authContAccess% rights to access the system resources %resNames%
		Parameter	Metric
		resNames: is a non-empty set of system resource	SystemResources: SystemResources = Set(SystemResource) SystemResource = Domain(Document, Section, Database,...)
		authContAccess: is a non-empty set of system control access types	ControlAccessTypes: ControlAccessTypes = Set(ControlAccessType) ControlAccessType = Domain(Read, Write, Execute, ...)
	userProfiles: is a non-empty set of user profiles. It must hold that their values are contained in the domains defined with the extensions above.	UserProfiles: UserProfiles = Set(UserProfile) UserProfile = Domain(Administrator, Author, User, ...)	
	Extended Part <i>Authorization Rules Customization</i>	Form text	The system shall allow an administrator to define authorization rules.
	Extended Part <i>Authorization Technology</i>	Form text	The authorization process shall be based on the %authMechanism% authorization mechanism
		Parameter	Metric
		authMechanism: is an authorization software technology	AuthorizationTechnology: AuthorizationTechnology = Domain(Active Directory, Novell eDirectory, OpenDirectory, ...)

4.1 Sets

- *Users*: Set of all users.
- *SystemResources*: Set of system resources.
- *AuthContAccess*: Set of authorization control accesses.
- $Admin \subseteq Users$: Subset of administrative users.
- *UserProfiles*: Set of user profile types.
- *AuthMechanisms*: Set of authorization mechanisms.

4.2 Predicates

- $accessRequest(u, r)$: Predicate indicating that user u has requested access to system resource r .
- $accessCheck(u, r)$: Predicate indicating that the access check for user u on resource r has been performed.
- $resourceRequires(p, c)$: Predicate indicating that authorization control access c is required to access resource r .
- $verifyRequisites(u, c, r)$: Predicate indicating that it has been verified that user u holds authorization control access c for resource r .
- $permitted(u, r)$: Predicate indicating that user u has been granted access to resource r .
- $permitted(u, r, c)$: Predicate indicating that user u has been granted access of type c to resource r .
- $denied(u, r)$: Predicate indicating that access to resource r has been denied to user u .
- $auth(u)$: Predicate indicating that the authentication process has been initiated for user u .
- $hasProfile(u, pr)$: Predicate indicating that user u has been assigned profile type pr .
- $recognize(u, pr)$: Predicate indicating that user u has been recognized as having profile type pr .
- $definesProfile(a, u, pr)$: Predicate indicating that admin a assigns profile pr to user u .
- $definesProfileResources(a, pr, r)$: Predicate indicating that admin a assigns access to resources r to users with profile pr .
- $setAuthResources(r, pr)$: Predicate indicating that it has been configured that users with profile type pr may access resource r .
- $configuredAuth(m)$: Predicate indicating that authorization technology m has been configured or enabled.

- $authorizeWith(u, m)$: Predicate indicating that the authorization process for user u has been executed using technology m .
- $setAuthContAccess(pr, r, c)$: Predicate indicating that authorization control c has been set for profile type pr to access resource r .

4.3 Formalization of the Fixed Part

$$\forall u \in Users. \forall r \in SystemResources. \mathbf{G} \left(accessRequest(u, r) \rightarrow \mathbf{F} accessCheck(u, r) \right)$$

4.4 Formalization of the Extended Parts

4.4.1 Authorization Control Access

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall u \in Users. \forall r \in SystemResources. \forall c \in AuthContAccess. \\ & \mathbf{G} \left((accessRequest(u, r) \wedge resourceRequires(c, r)) \rightarrow \right. \\ & \left. \mathbf{F}(verifyRequisites(u, c, r) \wedge \mathbf{X}(permitted(u, r) \vee denied(u, r))) \right) \end{aligned}$$

4.4.2 Authorization Control Access Customization

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall a \in Admin. \forall r \in SystemResources. \forall c \in AuthContAccess \\ & \mathbf{G} \left(definesAccessPolicy(a, c, r) \rightarrow \mathbf{X} resourcesRequires(c, r) \right) \\ & \quad \wedge \\ & \forall r \in SystemResources. \forall c \in AuthContAccess. \exists a \in Admin. \\ & \mathbf{G} \left(resourcesRequires(c, r) \rightarrow definesAccessPolicy(a, c, r) \right) \end{aligned}$$

4.4.3 Authorization Profiles

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall u \in Users. \forall pr \in UserProfiles. \\ & \mathbf{G} \left(auth(u) \wedge hasProfile(u, pr) \rightarrow \mathbf{F}(recognize(u, pr)) \right) \\ & \quad \wedge \\ & \mathbf{G} \left(recognize(u, pr) \rightarrow hasProfile(u, pr) \right) \end{aligned}$$

4.4.4 Authorization Profiles Customization

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall a \in Admin. \forall u \in Users. \forall up \in UserProfiles. \\ & \left(\text{definesProfile}(a, u, pr) \rightarrow \mathbf{F} \text{ hasProfile}(u, pr) \right) \\ & \quad \wedge \\ & \forall u \in Users. \forall up \in UserProfiles. \exists a \in Admin. \\ & \left(\text{hasProfile}(u, pr) \rightarrow \text{definesProfile}(a, u, pr) \right) \end{aligned}$$

4.4.5 Authorization Resources

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall u \in Users. \forall pr \in UserProfiles. \forall r \in SystemResources. \\ & \mathbf{G} \left(\text{accessRequest}(u, r) \wedge \text{hasProfile}(u, pr) \wedge \text{setAuthResources}(pr, r) \rightarrow \right. \\ & \quad \left. \mathbf{X} \text{ permitted}(u, r) \right) \\ & \quad \wedge \\ & \forall u \in Users. \forall r \in SystemResources. \exists pr \in UserProfiles. \\ & \mathbf{G} \left(\text{permitted}(u, r) \rightarrow \text{hasProfile}(u, pr) \wedge \text{setAuthResources}(pr, r) \right) \end{aligned}$$

4.4.6 Authorization Resources Customization

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall a \in Admins. \forall pr \in UserProfiles. \forall r \in SystemResources. \\ & \mathbf{G} \left(\text{definesProfileResources}(a, pr, r) \rightarrow \mathbf{F} \text{ setAuthResources}(pr, r) \right) \\ & \quad \wedge \\ & \forall pr \in UserProfiles. \forall r \in SystemResources. \exists a \in Admins. \\ & \mathbf{G} \left(\text{setAuthResources}(pr, r) \rightarrow \text{definesProfileResources}(a, pr, r) \right) \end{aligned}$$

4.4.7 Authorization Technology

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall u \in Users. \forall m \in AuthMechanism. \\ & \mathbf{G} \left(\left(\text{accessRequest}(u, r) \wedge \text{configuredAuth}(m) \right) \rightarrow \mathbf{X} \text{ authorizeWith}(u, m) \right) \end{aligned}$$

4.4.8 Authorization Rules

$$\forall u \in Users \forall r \in SystemResources \forall c \in AuthContAccess \forall pr \in UserProfiles$$
$$\mathbf{G} \left((accessRequest(u, r) \wedge hasProfile(u, pr) \wedge setAuthContAccess(pr, r, c)) \rightarrow \right.$$
$$\left. \mathbf{X} permitted(u, r, c) \right)$$

^

$$\forall u \in Users \forall r \in SystemResources \forall c \in AuthContAccess \exists pr \in UserProfiles$$
$$\mathbf{G} \left(permitted(u, r, c) \rightarrow (hasProfile(u, pr) \wedge setAuthContAccess(p, r, c)) \right)$$

4.4.9 Authorization Rules Customization

$$\forall pr \in UserProfiles \forall r \in SystemResources \forall c \in AuthContAccess \forall a \in Admin$$

$$\mathbf{G} \left(wantsToAssign(a, pr, r, c) \rightarrow \mathbf{X} setAuthContAccess(pr, r, c) \right)$$

^

$$\forall p \in UserProfiles. \forall r \in SystemResources. \forall c \in AuthContAccess. \exists a \in Admin.$$

$$\mathbf{G} \left(setAuthContAccess(pr, r, c) \rightarrow wantsToAssign(a, pr, r, c) \right)$$

5 Automatic Logoff

Requirement Pattern <i>Automatic Logoff</i>	Description	This pattern expresses the need of dropping off inactive connections under a time-based policy	
	Comments	—	
	Pattern goal	Maintain the security of the system	
	Author	GESSI-SSI	
	Sources (0..*)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement books from SSI • Specialized literature 	
	Keywords (0..*)	—	
Requirement Form <i>Automatic Logoff</i>	Dependencies (0..*)	—	
	Description	This form expresses the general need of logging off automatically. Extensions exist to state the inactivity time for disconnection, and also for requiring this time to be customizable	
	Comments	Application of extensions: Logoff Time, Customizable Logoff Time: may be applied at most once each.	
	Version date	2009-03-20 00:00:00.0	
	Author	GESSI-SSI	
	Sources (0..*)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement books from SSI • Specialized literature 	
	Fixed Part	Form text	The system shall drop off inactive connections
	Extended Part <i>Customizable Logoff Time</i>	Form text	The inactivity time before automatic logoff shall be customizable
	Extended Part <i>Logoff Time</i>	Form text	The system shall logoff automatically sessions that are inactive since more than %amountOfTime% %timeUnit%
			Parameter
		timeUnit: is a unit of time corresponding to the units of frequency for loggin off	TimeUnitType: TimeUnitType = Domain(Days, Hours, Minutes, Seconds, Miliseconds, ...)
		amountOfTime: is a number that indicates time duration	AmountOfUnitType: AmountOfUnitType = Integer

5.1 Sets

- *Sessions*: Set of all sessions.
- *TimeoutValues*: Set of admissible timeout values (e.g., integers expressed in minutes).
- *Users*: Set of all users.

5.2 Predicates

- *inactiveSession(s)*: Predicate indicating that session s has been started.
- *logoff(s)*: Predicate indicating that an automatic *logoff* has occurred for session s .
- *setLogoffTimeout(τ)*: Predicate indicating that the operation to set the timeout value τ has been initiated.
- *configuredLogoffTimeout(τ)*: Predicate indicating that the timeout value τ has been set.
- *loggedIn(u)*: Predicate indicating that user u is logged in.
- *interact(u)*: Predicate indicating that user u has performed an interaction.
- *expire(u)*: Predicate indicating that user u 's timeout has expired.

5.3 Variables

- *amountOfTime*: Integer > 0 , with maximum value $MAX_INTEGER$ (unit of measure: minutes).
- τ_{\max} : Total inactivity timeout (unit of measure: steps or time units).

5.4 Formalization of the Fixed Part

$$\forall s \in Sessions \mathbf{G} \left(inactiveSession(s) \rightarrow \mathbf{F} logoff(s) \right)$$

5.5 Formalization of the Extended Parts

5.5.1 Customizable Logoff Time

$\forall \tau \in \text{TimeoutValues}.$

$$\mathbf{G} \left(\text{setLogoffTimeout}(\tau) \rightarrow \mathbf{X} \text{ configuredLogoffTimeout}(\tau) \right)$$

5.5.2 Logoff Time

$\forall u \in \text{Users}. \forall \tau \in \text{TimeoutValues}.$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{G} \left((\text{loggedIn}(u) \wedge \text{configuredLogoffTimeout}(\tau)) \right. \\ \left. \rightarrow \right. \\ \left. (\mathbf{F}_{\leq \tau} \text{interacts}(u) \vee \mathbf{F}_{=\tau} \text{expire}(u)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

6 Data Transmission Protection

Requirement Pattern <i>Data Transmission Protection</i>	Description	This pattern expresses the need of protecting system data when transmitted outside of system boundaries		
	Comments	—		
	Pattern goal	Keep system data secure when transmitting it outside of its boundaries		
	Author	GESSI-SSI		
	Sources (0..*)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement books from SSI • Specialized literature 		
	Keywords (0..*)	Encryption, Secured Data, Secured Transmissions, security		
	Dependencies (0..*)	—		
Requirement Form <i>Protection when Transmission of Data with Systems or Networks</i>	Description	This form declares the general concept of protection when there are transmission of data with other systems or networks. An extension is included that requires an specific way of protection that is encryption (one for transmission to systems and another one over networks).		
	Comments	Application of extensions: Communication with systems, Encryption when communicating with systems, Transmission over networks, Encryption over networks: may be applied at most once each.		
	Version date	2009-03-20 00:00:00.0		
	Author	GESSI-SSI		
	Sources (0..*)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement books from SSI • Specialized literature 		
	Fixed Part	Form text	The system shall protect data transmitted to other systems	
	Extended Part <i>Communication with Systems</i>	Form text	Protection is mandatory when data are transmitted to %extSystems% external systems	
		Parameter	Metric	
		extSystems: is a non-empty set of software names (systems, databases, etc.)	SoftwareNames: SoftwareNames = Set(SoftwareName) SoftwareName = String	
	Extended Part <i>Encryption over Networks</i>	Form text	Encryption is mandatory when data are transmitted over %netTypes% networks.	
		Parameter	Metric	
		netTypes: is a non-empty set of different types of networks	NetworkTypes: NetworkTypes = Set(NetworkType) NetworkType = Domain(Internal, Internet, Extranet, Intranet, ...)	
	Extended Part <i>Encryption when Communicating with Systems</i>	Form text	Encryption is mandatory when data are transmitted to %extSystems% external systems	
		Parameter	Metric	
		extSystems: is a non-empty set of software names (systems, databases, etc.)	SoftwareNames: SoftwareNames = Set(SoftwareName) SoftwareName = String	
	Extended Part <i>Transmission over networks</i>	Form text	Protection is mandatory when data are transmitted over %netTypes% networks.	
		Parameter	Metric	
netTypes: is a non-empty set of different types of networks		NetworkTypes: NetworkTypes = Set(NetworkType) NetworkType = Domain(Internal, Internet, Extranet, Intranet, ...)		

6.1 Sets

- *Data*: Set of transmitted data.
- *Systems*: Set of systems.
- *extSystems* \subseteq *Systems*: Set of external systems.
- *NetworkTypes*: Set of network types.

6.2 Predicates

- *transmitted(data)*: Predicate indicating that transmission of *data* has started.
- *target(data, s)*: Predicate indicating that *data* have been sent to system *s*.
- *protected(data)*: Predicate indicating that *data* have been placed under protection.
- *over(data, n)*: Predicate indicating that *data* have been transmitted over network type *n*.
- *encrypted(data)*: Predicate indicating that *data* have been encrypted.

6.3 Formalization of the Fixed Part

$$\forall data \in Data. \mathbf{G} \left(transmitted(data) \rightarrow protected(data) \right)$$

6.4 Formalization of the Extended Parts

6.4.1 Communication with Systems

$$\forall data \in Data. \forall s \in extSystems. \mathbf{G} \left(\left(transmitted(data) \wedge target(data, s) \right) \rightarrow protected(data) \right)$$

6.4.2 Encryption Over Networks

$$\forall data \in Data \forall n \in NetworkTypes \mathbf{G} \left(\left(transmitted(data) \wedge over(data, n) \right) \rightarrow encrypted(data) \right)$$

6.4.3 Encryption when Communicating with Systems

$\forall data \in Data \forall s \in extSystems$

$$\mathbf{G} \left((transmitted(data) \wedge target(data, s)) \rightarrow encrypted(data) \right)$$

6.4.4 Transmission Over Networks

$\forall data \in Data \forall n \in NetworkTypes$

$$\mathbf{G} \left((transmitted(data) \wedge over(data, n)) \rightarrow protected(data) \right)$$

7 Stored Data Protection

Requirement Pattern <i>Stored Data Protection</i>	Description	This pattern expresses the need of protecting system data from unauthorized access				
	Comments	—				
	Pattern goal	Protect system data from unauthorized access				
	Author	GESSI-SSI				
	Sources (0..*)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement books from SSI • Specialized literature 				
	Keywords (0..*)	—				
Requirement Form <i>Data Protection</i>	Description	—				
	Comments	Application of extensions: Data Encryption: may be applied at most once each.				
	Version date	2009-03-20 00:00:00.0				
	Author	GESSI-SSI				
	Sources (0..*)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement books from SSI • Specialized literature 				
	Fixed Part	Form text	%data% kept in the system shall not be accessible to unauthorized user profiles or to people attempting to access from outside the system			
Extended Part <i>Data Encryption</i>		Form text	All %data% kept in the system shall be encrypted			
		<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Metric</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>data: is a non-empty set of types of data that are managed by the system</td> <td>DataDescriptors: DataDescriptors = Set(DataDescriptor) DataDescriptor = Domain(Personal Data, Financial Data, ...)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Metric	data: is a non-empty set of types of data that are managed by the system	DataDescriptors: DataDescriptors = Set(DataDescriptor) DataDescriptor = Domain(Personal Data, Financial Data, ...)
Parameter	Metric					
data: is a non-empty set of types of data that are managed by the system	DataDescriptors: DataDescriptors = Set(DataDescriptor) DataDescriptor = Domain(Personal Data, Financial Data, ...)					

7.1 Sets

- *Data*: Set of data.

7.2 Predicates

- *stored(data)*: Predicate indicating that *data* have been stored.

- $encrypted(data)$: Predicate indicating that $data$ have been encrypted.

7.3 Formalization of the Fixed Part

$$\forall data \in Data. \mathbf{G} \left(stored(data) \rightarrow protected(data) \right)$$

7.4 Formalization of the Extended Part

7.4.1 Data Encryption

$$\forall data \in Data. \mathbf{G} \left(stored(data) \rightarrow encrypted(data) \right)$$